

The Inverse Problem of Probabilistic Analysis of Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Composites

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Abstract

A probabilistic analysis in micromechanics was developed previously to predict the probability distributions for the mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites. The analysis has provided a non-traditional approach to eliminate the unnecessary material fabrications for those to-be-fabricated composites which do not meet the application requirements based on the analysis and to significantly reduce the time and cost of material development. In practical, the minute-scale cross section of the fiber makes the mechanical properties of the fiber very difficult or even impossible to measure, particularly the transverse Young's modulus or the Poisson's ratio. The knowledge of the probability distributions of the fiber mechanical properties may have to come from an inverse probabilistic analysis of an existing material system with the same fiber. In this presentation, the inverse probabilistic analysis is established to predict the probability density functions of the fiber's mechanical properties from the observed probability distributions of the matrix and their unidirectional composite, and compared with the observed histograms of the test data measured.

In materials research, Weibull distribution, in addition to normal distribution, is popularly used for composite materials mechanical properties. In previous technical reports, we used the probabilistic micromechanics analysis to predict the probability distributions for the mechanical properties of IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites, with the observed (curve-fitting) Weibull and normal probability density functions of the mechanical properties of the IM-7 carbon fiber and 5250-4 BMI matrix. We compared the predicted probability distributions of the mechanical properties of IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional fiber-reinforced with the histograms of the test results. In this article, we will use the inverse probabilistic micromechanics analysis to predict the probability distributions for the mechanical properties of the IM-7 carbon fiber, with the observed Weibull and normal probability density functions of the mechanical properties of 5250-4 BMI matrix and IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites. We will compare the predicted probability distributions of the mechanical properties of IM-7 carbon fiber as it behaves within the composite with the histograms of the test results for the individual pre-fabricated fiber.

This complete cycle of probabilistic (and inverse probabilistic) micromechanics analysis provides a screening tool to help material producers to eliminate the unnecessary time-consuming and costly material fabrications and to reduce the numbers of testing to a minimum but enough to verify the model prediction. And consequently, it provides a means to accelerate the insertion of materials into production systems.

Key Terms: Probabilistic Methods, Micromechanics Model, Unidirectional Composites, Mechanical Properties, Probability Density Function

1. Introduction

Insertion of advanced composite materials into Air Force (AF) production systems requires extensive testing of mechanical and other physical properties at the coupon, element, subcomponent, and component levels. The material development becomes a time-consuming and costly task, and new

material insertion into production is extremely difficult, typically taking 15 to 20 years. To accelerate the insertion of composite materials into AF production systems at a much lower cost, a means must be established to preclude premature material fabrications and reduce material testing to a minimum but enough to manage the uncertainties in material development. The micromechanics approach has been widely used to predict the mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites from the mechanical properties and volume fractions of the constituents – fiber and matrix [1,2]. However, these mechanical properties of the fiber, matrix and composite in these micromechanics formulations are random variables. They should be analyzed based on the probability and random variable analysis method [3] instead of being analyzed deterministically. The probability and random variable analysis approach has been widely used in many technical areas, such as vibration, system control, structural dynamics, earthquake engineering, biomedical engineering, etc. Applications of random variable analysis in micromechanics of composite materials in the prediction of the probability density functions of mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites had been attempted in Chuang [4].

However, in practical circumstances, the minute-scale cross section of the fiber makes the mechanical properties of the fiber very difficult or even impossible to measure, particularly the transverse Young's modulus or the Poisson's ratio. The knowledge of the probability distributions of the fiber mechanical properties in [4] may have to come from an inverse probabilistic analysis of an existing material system with the same fiber. The inverse predictions of the fiber's mechanical properties from those of matrix and unidirectional composite, in deterministic approach, had been considered in many articles [5,6,7]. In this article, the inverse probabilistic analysis is established to predict, from the observed Weibull and normal probability distributions of 5250-4 BMI matrix and IM-7/5250-4 composite, the probability density functions of the IM-7 carbon fiber's mechanical properties as it behaves within the composite. The histogram of individual pre-fabricated fibers is observed for comparison.

The following assumptions are used in the micromechanics modeling of the unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite. It assumes that there are no voids in the composite and that perfect bonding exists between fibers and matrix. The unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite behaves like a homogeneous anisotropic material with transversely isotropic. The effective mechanical properties of the unidirectional composite are functions of the fiber and matrix mechanical properties, their volume fractions, and perhaps also the statistical parameters associated with fiber distribution.

It is generally observed that fiber-reinforced composite specimens exhibit less variability in tensile strength than their constituent fibers and matrix. In continuous fiber-reinforced composites, the load of a failed fiber is redistributed onto surviving fibers. We also anticipated a much narrowly spread test data for the fiber-reinforced composite mechanical properties because of their failure mechanism in the balance of stresses between broken fibers and neighboring fibers, and interfaces between fibers and matrix. Therefore, our inverse predictions of the probabilistic distributions for the mechanical properties of fibers as they behave within the composite will be more narrowly distributed than the test data for the individual pre-fabricated fibers.

2. Probabilistic micromechanics model

The rule of mixtures in micromechanics of composites has been widely used to predict the mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites [1,2]. However, these mechanical properties of fiber, matrix, and composite are random variables and can be readily analyzed from the probabilistic analysis approach [3]. In order to introduce the applications of probability and random variable analysis in micromechanics of organic matrix composites, we use the rule of mixtures in micromechanics in this report for demonstration simplicity. Later, we will apply this approach to a more complicated micromechanics analysis of randomly oriented laminated composites in a later report.

With the assumption of no voids in the composites, the volume fractions of fiber and matrix V_f and V_m satisfy the following equation.

$$V_f + V_m = 1 \quad (1)$$

(Throughout this article, the subscripts f and m will be used to identify the properties of the fiber and matrix.) With the assumption of perfect bonding between fibers and matrix, the stresses ($\mathbf{s}_f, \mathbf{s}_m, \mathbf{s}_x$) and Young's modulus (E_f, E_m, E_x) of fiber, matrix, and unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite in the longitudinal direction x satisfy the following equations.

$$\mathbf{s}_x = V_f \mathbf{s}_f + V_m \mathbf{s}_m \quad \rightarrow \quad \mathbf{s}_f = \frac{1}{V_f} \mathbf{s}_x - \frac{V_m}{V_f} \mathbf{s}_m \quad (2)$$

$$E_x = V_f E_f + V_m E_m \quad \rightarrow \quad E_f = \frac{1}{V_f} E_x - \frac{V_m}{V_f} E_m \quad (3)$$

In Equations (1-3), V_f and V_m are assumed to be deterministic values, and $\mathbf{s}_x, \mathbf{s}_f, \mathbf{s}_m, E_x, E_f$ and E_m are random variables with PDFs $f_{\mathbf{s}_x}(\mathbf{s}_x), f_{\mathbf{s}_f}(\mathbf{s}_f), f_{\mathbf{s}_m}(\mathbf{s}_m), f_{E_x}(E_x), f_{E_f}(E_f)$, and $f_{E_m}(E_m)$.

Therefore, the PDFs of \mathbf{s}_f and E_f in terms of Equations (2-3) as derived in [2] are as follows

$$f_{\mathbf{s}_f}(\mathbf{s}_f) = V_f \int_0^{\infty} f_{\mathbf{s}_x}(V_f \mathbf{s}_f + V_m \mathbf{s}_m) f_{\mathbf{s}_m}(\mathbf{s}_m) d\mathbf{s}_m \quad (4)$$

and

$$f_{E_f}(E_f) = V_f \int_0^{\infty} f_{E_x}(V_f E_f + V_m E_m) f_{E_m}(E_m) dE_m \quad (5)$$

where the volume fractions of fiber and matrix V_f and V_m are deterministic values.

There are two mechanical properties of the fiber, \mathbf{n}_f and G_f , the Poisson's ratio and shear modulus, are very important but can not be measured. However, they can be derived from the observed data for matrix and composite, $\mathbf{n}_m, \mathbf{n}_x, G_m$, and G_x , where \mathbf{n}_x and G_x are abbreviated notations for $\mathbf{n}_{x y}$ and $G_{x y}$.

The Poisson's ratio \mathbf{n}_f follows the rule of mixtures, as follows

$$\mathbf{n}_x = V_f \mathbf{n}_f + V_m \mathbf{n}_m \quad \rightarrow \quad \mathbf{n}_f = \frac{1}{V_f} \mathbf{n}_x - \frac{V_m}{V_f} \mathbf{n}_m \quad (6)$$

The PDF's for \mathbf{n}_f as derived in [2] is

$$f_{\mathbf{n}_f}(\mathbf{n}_f) = \frac{V_f}{V_m} \int_0^\infty f_{\mathbf{n}_m} \left(\frac{\mathbf{n}_x - V_f \mathbf{n}_f}{V_m} \right) f_{\mathbf{n}_x}(\mathbf{n}_x) d\mathbf{n}_x \quad (7)$$

For composites with an anisotropic fiber, Hashin [12] had derived the following equation for the shear modulus G_f

$$G_x = G_m + \frac{V_f}{\frac{1}{G_f - G_m} + \frac{V_m}{2G_m}} \quad \rightarrow \quad G_f = G_m + \frac{1}{\frac{V_f}{G_x - G_m} - \frac{V_m}{2G_m}} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the PDFs for G_f as derived in [2] is as follows

$$f_{G_f}(G_f) = \frac{V_f V_m}{2} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{(G_f - G_m)^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{Y^2 \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)^2} f_{G_m} \left[\frac{V_m}{2 \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)} \right] \int_0^\infty f_{G_m} \left(G_x - \frac{V_f}{Y} \right) f_{G_x}(G_x) dG_x dY f_{G_m}(G_m) dG_m \quad (9)$$

3. Observed mechanical properties

To demonstrate the applications of the inverse probabilistic micromechanics analysis to IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite, an in-house test program was established to measure the mechanical properties \mathbf{s}_f , \mathbf{e}_f and E_f of IM-7 carbon fiber, \mathbf{s}_m , \mathbf{e}_m , E_m , \mathbf{n}_m and G_m of 5250-4 BMI matrix, and \mathbf{s}_x , \mathbf{e}_x , E_x , E_y , \mathbf{n}_x and G_x of IM-7/ 5250-4 unidirectional fiber reinforced composite.

The 5250-4 BMI matrix specimens were prepared and tested in accordance with ASTM test procedure D638. There were 60 specimens tested at room temperature. A FORTRAN computer program was developed to detect the outliers of the test results [8], and to calculate the frequencies of the histograms for the remaining specimens. The histograms for \mathbf{s}_m , \mathbf{e}_m , E_m , and G_m of the remaining 57 5250-4 BMI matrix specimens are shown in Figure 1 together with the fitted Weibull and normal PDFs. Because of the fair size of the population in this test program, it seems that the normal distributions fit the histograms a little better than the Weibull distributions.

The longitudinal unidirectional composite specimens were prepared with the configuration of an eight-ply rectangular test specimen that was 0.5 inch wide and 10 inches long, and were tested in accordance with ASTM test procedure D3039. There are 63 specimens, with $V_f = 0.63$, tested at room temperature. A FORTRAN computer program was used to detect the outliers of the test results, and to calculate the frequencies of the histograms for the remaining 62 specimens. The histograms for \mathbf{S}_x , \mathbf{e}_x , and E_x of IM-7/5250-4 composite specimens are shown in Figure 2, together with the fitted Weibull and normal PDFs. Again, because of the fair size of the population in this test program, it seems that the normal distributions fit the histograms a little better than the Weibull distributions.

The transverse composite specimens were prepared with the configuration of an eight-ply rectangular test specimen that was 0.5 inch wide and 10 inches long, and were tested in accordance with ASTM test procedure D3039. There were 61 specimens, with $V_f = 0.56$, tested at room temperature. A FORTRAN computer program was used to detect the outliers of the test results and to calculate the frequencies of the histogram for the remaining 59 specimens. The histogram for E_y of IM-7/5250-4 composite specimens is also shown in Figure 2, together with the fitted Weibull and normal PDFs. Again, because of the fair size of the population in this test program, it seems that the normal distributions fit the histograms a little better than the Weibull distributions.

The 45° angle-ply composite specimens were prepared with the configuration of an eight-ply rectangular test specimen that was 0.065 inch thick and 8 inches long, and were tested in accordance with ASTM test procedure D3518 to measure G_x of IM-7/5250-4 composite. There were 57 specimens, with $V_f = 0.56$, tested at room temperature. A FORTRAN computer program was used to detect the outliers of the test results, and to calculate the frequencies of the histogram for the remaining 52 specimens. The histogram for G_x of IM-7/5250-4 composite specimens is shown in Figure 2, together with the fitted Weibull and normal PDFs. Again, because of the fair size of the population in this test program, it seems that the normal distributions fit the histograms a little better than the Weibull distributions.

4. Application

(A) Normal Distribution:

As shown in Section 3, the observed mechanical properties of 5250-4 BMI matrix and IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite fit normal distribution fairly well. In this section, the PDFs for \mathbf{S}_m , E_m , and \mathbf{n}_m of 5250-4 BMI matrix and \mathbf{S}_x , E_x , E_y , \mathbf{n}_x , and G_x of IM-7/5250-4 composite in normal distribution formats are input to the equations in Section 2 to derive the PDFs for \mathbf{S}_f , E_f , \mathbf{n}_f , and G_f of IM-7 fiber.

The normal distribution curves and their means and standard deviations for the matrix and composite PDFs are shown in Figures 1 and 2. These PDFs are presented in the normal PDF format as follows.

$$f_x(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}s_x} \exp\left[-\frac{(x-m_x)^2}{2s_x^2}\right] \quad (10)$$

The means m and standard deviations s for the above PDFs are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

In general, Equation (10) with specific mean and standard deviation values for each mechanical property of 5250-4 BMI matrix and IM-7/5250-4 fiber-reinforced composite can be input into equations in Section 2 to obtain the predicted PDFs for IM-7 carbon fiber in closed form or in integration formulas.

Therefore, the normal PDFs for \mathbf{s}_f and E_f of the fiber are governed by the following equations.

$$f_{\mathbf{s}_f}(\mathbf{s}_f) = \frac{V_f}{\sqrt{2\mathbf{p}(s_{\mathbf{s}_x}^2 - V_m^2 s_{\mathbf{s}_m}^2)}} \exp \left[-\frac{V_f^2 (\mathbf{s}_f - \frac{1}{V_f} m_{\mathbf{s}_x} + \frac{V_m}{V_f} m_{\mathbf{s}_m})^2}{2(s_{\mathbf{s}_x}^2 - V_m^2 s_{\mathbf{s}_m}^2)} \right] \quad (11)$$

and

$$f_{E_f}(E_f) = \frac{V_f}{\sqrt{2\mathbf{p}(s_{E_x}^2 - V_m^2 s_{E_m}^2)}} \exp \left[-\frac{V_f^2 (E_f - \frac{1}{V_f} m_{E_x} + \frac{V_m}{V_f} m_{E_m})^2}{2(s_{E_x}^2 - V_m^2 s_{E_m}^2)} \right] \quad (12)$$

The PDFs for \mathbf{n}_f and G_f as predicted inversely from those of matrix and composite mechanical properties are as follows.

$$f_{\mathbf{n}_f}(\mathbf{n}_f) = \frac{V_f}{\sqrt{2\mathbf{p}(s_{\mathbf{n}_x}^2 - V_m^2 s_{\mathbf{n}_m}^2)}} \exp \left[-\frac{V_f^2 (\mathbf{n}_f - \frac{1}{V_f} m_{\mathbf{n}_x} + \frac{V_m}{V_f} m_{\mathbf{n}_m})^2}{2(s_{\mathbf{n}_x}^2 - V_m^2 s_{\mathbf{n}_m}^2)} \right] \quad (13)$$

and

$$f_{G_f}(G_f) = \frac{V_f V_m}{2(\sqrt{2\mathbf{p}})^3 s_{G_m}^2 \sqrt{s_{G_x}^2 - s_{G_m}^2}} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{(G_f - G_m)^2} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{Y^2 \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)^2} \exp \left[-\frac{\left(\frac{V_m}{2 \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)} - m_{G_m} \right)^2}{2s_{G_m}^2} - \frac{\left(\frac{V_f}{Y} - m_{G_x} + m_{G_m} \right)^2}{2(s_{G_x}^2 - s_{G_m}^2)} \right] dY \exp \left[-\frac{(G_m - m_{G_m})^2}{2s_{G_m}^2} \right] dG_m \quad (14)$$

(B) Weibull Distributions

As shown in Section 3, the observed mechanical properties of 5250-4 BMI matrix and IM-7/5250-4 fiber-reinforced composite can be fitted by Weibull distributions. In this section, the PDFs for \mathbf{s}_m , E_m and \mathbf{n}_m of 5250-4 BMI matrix and \mathbf{s}_x , E_x , E_y , \mathbf{n}_x , and G_x of IM-7/5250-4 composite in Weibull distribution formats are input to the equations in Section 2 to derive the PDFs for \mathbf{s}_f , E_f , \mathbf{n}_f , and G_f of IM-7 fiber. The Weibull distribution for the matrix and composite PDFs are shown in Figures 4, 5 and 6. These PDFs are presented in the Weibull PDF format

$$f_x(x) = \frac{\mathbf{b}_x}{\mathbf{a}_x} \left(\frac{x}{\mathbf{a}_x} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_x - 1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{x}{\mathbf{a}_x} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_x} \right] \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{a} is a scale parameter and \mathbf{b} is a shape parameter.

Equation (15) for each mechanical property of 5250-4 BMI matrix and IM-7/5250-4 fiber-reinforced composite can be input into equations in Section 2 to obtain the predicted PDFs for IM-7 fiber in the integration formulas. Therefore, the PDFs for \mathbf{s}_f and E_f of IM-7 carbon fiber are governed by the following equations.

$$f_{\mathbf{s}_f}(\mathbf{s}_f) = \frac{V_f \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s}_x} \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s}_m}}{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{s}_x} \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{s}_m}} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{V_f \mathbf{s}_f + V_m \mathbf{s}_m}{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{s}_x}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s}_x} - 1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{V_f \mathbf{s}_f + V_m \mathbf{s}_m}{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{s}_x}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s}_x}} \right] \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_m}{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{s}_m}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s}_m} - 1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_m}{\mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{s}_m}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{s}_m}} \right] \cdot d\mathbf{s}_m \quad (16)$$

and

$$f_{E_f}(E_f) = \frac{V_f \mathbf{b}_{E_x} \mathbf{b}_{E_m}}{\mathbf{a}_{E_x} \mathbf{a}_{E_m}} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{V_f E_f + V_m E_m}{\mathbf{a}_{E_x}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{E_x} - 1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{V_f E_f + V_m E_m}{\mathbf{a}_{E_x}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{E_x}} \right] \cdot \left(\frac{E_m}{\mathbf{a}_{E_m}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{E_m} - 1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{E_m}{\mathbf{a}_{E_m}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{E_m}} \right] \cdot dE_m \quad (17)$$

The PDFs for \mathbf{n}_f and G_f are predicted inversely from those of matrix and composite mechanical properties. They are as follows.

$$f_{\mathbf{n}_f}(\mathbf{n}_f) = \frac{V_f \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{n}_x} \mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{n}_m}}{V_m \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{n}_x} \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{n}_m}} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{\mathbf{n}_x - V_f \mathbf{n}_f}{V_m \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{n}_m}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{n}_m} - 1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\mathbf{n}_x - V_f \mathbf{n}_f}{V_m \mathbf{a}_{\mathbf{n}_m}} \right)^{\mathbf{b}_{\mathbf{n}_m}} \right] \cdot d\mathbf{n}_f$$

$$\left(\frac{\mathbf{n}_x}{\mathbf{a}_{n_x}} \right)^{b_{n_x}-1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\mathbf{n}_x}{\mathbf{a}_{n_x}} \right)^{b_{n_x}} \right] \cdot d\mathbf{n}_x \quad (18)$$

and

$$f_{G_f}(G_f) = \frac{V_f V_m \mathbf{b}_{G_x} \mathbf{b}_{G_m}^3}{2\mathbf{a}_{G_x} \mathbf{a}_{G_m}^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{(G_f - G_m)^2} \left(\frac{G_m}{\mathbf{a}_{G_m}} \right)^{b_{G_m}-1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{G_m}{\mathbf{a}_{G_m}} \right)^{b_{G_m}} \right] \cdot \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{Y^2 \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)^2} \left(\frac{V_m}{2\mathbf{a}_{G_m} \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)} \right)^{b_{G_m}-1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{V_m}{2\mathbf{a}_{G_m} \left(Y - \frac{1}{G_f - G_m} \right)} \right)^{b_{G_m}} \right] \cdot \int_0^\infty \left(\frac{G_x - \frac{V_f}{Y}}{\mathbf{a}_{G_m}} \right)^{b_{G_m}-1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{G_x - \frac{V_f}{Y}}{\mathbf{a}_{G_m}} \right)^{b_{G_m}} \right] \cdot \left(\frac{G_x}{\mathbf{a}_{G_x}} \right)^{b_{G_x}-1} \cdot \exp \left[- \left(\frac{G_x}{\mathbf{a}_{G_x}} \right)^{b_{G_x}} \right] \cdot dG_x \cdot dY \cdot dG_m \quad (19)$$

5. Model prediction

In this section, the probability density functions (PDFs) for the test data of \mathbf{s}_m , E_m , and \mathbf{n}_m of 5250-4 BMI matrix and \mathbf{s}_x , E_x , E_y , \mathbf{n}_x , and G_x of IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional composite in Weibull and normal distribution formats, as shown in Figures 1,2 and 3, are inserted in Equations 18-22 of Section 4 to obtain the predicted the PDFs for \mathbf{s}_f , E_f , \mathbf{n}_f , and G_f of IM-7 fiber as Shown in Figure 3. The volume fraction of IM-7 fiber in the IM-7/5052-4 composite is assumed to be a deterministic value which is normally between 0.55 – 0.65 in the laboratory fabrication environment.

The IM-7 fiber specimens were prepared in accordance with ASTM test procedure D3379. There were 19 lots, with 10 specimens for each lot, tested at room temperature. The test results for Lot 3-C specimens were discarded from further analysis because of the test equipment problems. A FORTRAN computer program was developed to detect the outliers of the test results, and to calculate the frequencies of the histograms for the remaining 18 lots of IM-7 fiber specimens. The histograms for \mathbf{s}_f and E_f of the remaining 18 lots of IM-7 fibers are shown in Figure 4 together with the fitted Weibull and normal PDFs. Because of the fair size of the population in this test program, it seems that the normal distributions fit the histograms a little better than the Weibull distributions.

6. Summary

In a previous report [4], a probabilistic analysis in the preliminary design of unidirectional fiber-reinforced composites, with the observed (or the knowledge of) normal probability distributions of the

mechanical properties of the constituent fiber and matrix, was presented to help accelerate the material insertion. In which a completed test program was established to obtain a statistical meaningful database for mechanical properties of IM-7 carbon fiber, 5250-4 Bismaleimide (BMI) matrix and IM-7/5250-4 unidirectional fiber-reinforced composite. In practical circumstances, the minute-scale cross section of the fiber makes the mechanical properties of the fiber very difficult or even impossible to measure, particularly the transverse Young's modulus or Poisson's ratio. In this article, a probabilistic micromechanics analysis was developed to inversely predict the probability density functions for the mechanical properties of fiber from an existing material system with the same fiber. These predicted PDFs of the fiber mechanical properties and those of new matrices can be used as the input to the preliminary design analysis developed in [4]. This complete cycle of probabilistic micromechanics analysis provides a screening tool to help material producers to eliminate the unnecessary material fabrications for those to-be-fabricated composites which do not meet the application requirements based on the analysis, and to reduce the numbers of testing to a minimum but enough to verify the model prediction. And consequently, it provides a means to accelerate the insertion of materials into AF weapon systems.

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5250-4 BMI Matrix

Figure 1. Histograms and Fitted Weibull and Normal Probability Density Functions for 5250-4 BMI Matrix Mechanical Properties Test Results

IM-7/5250-4 Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Composite

Figure 2. Histograms and Fitted Weibull and Normal Probability Density Functions for IM-7/5250-4 Unidirectional Fiber-Reinforced Composite Mechanical Properties Test Results

IM-7 Carbon Fiber

Figure 3. Predicted Probability Density Functions Based on Weibull and Normal Distributions of Mechanical Properties of Matrix and Unidirectional Composite

IM-7 Carbon Fiber

Figure 4. Histograms and Fitted Weibull and Normal Probability Density Functions for IM-7 Carbon Fiber Mechanical Property Test Results